

Real-Time Computer Vision Based Flood and Puddle Detection in Urban Areas

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doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20395637

Abstract: Urban flooding is a major threat to safety and city infrastructure. Early warning and rapid detection are vital to minimise damage and protect lives. However, distinguishing dangerous floods from harmless puddles remains challenging. This paper presents a real-time detection system for urban floods and puddles, using advanced computer vision and edge networking. The system is built on the YOLOv8 object detection model, which identifies and classifies floods and puddles in street-level scenes. A Milesight 5G-enabled camera streams high-resolution, low-latency video to the model, which enables prompt detection across urban areas. The model was developed using a curated dataset comprising 9,467 labeled images, which were sourced from the Roboflow platform. Careful selection and inclusion of non-flood backgrounds enhanced the model's ability to distinguish between flood events and ordinary water pooling. Training was structured with 70% of data for training, 20% for testing, and 10% for validation. The YOLOv8 model achieved a precision of approximately 90.6% in identifying flood scenes, with few false positives. Recall for water classes was 72.4%, indicating that smaller puddles may occasionally be missed. The system was tested with the Savonia University of Applied Sciences' private 5G network and Milesight camera infrastructure. This confirmed seamless real-time operation and demonstrated its suitability for integration with existing urban surveillance systems. These results show that combining YOLOv8 with 5G connectivity offers a robust, scalable approach to urban flood monitoring, supporting emergency response and infrastructure protection.

Keywords: urban flood; YOLO; safe infrastructure; 5G.

1 Introduction

Urban flooding (UF) is one of the deadliest natural hazards in the world. It may occur with no or little warning, within a few minutes and have the impact on humans, assets, and city infrastructure (Khan et al. 2018). UF have caused serious risks to human life with almost 5000 deaths every year (Duong et al. 2021). One of the major causes of these floods are heavy rains due to climate changes. These floods can carry many materials such as trees, rocks, and debris which results in more damage to the city infrastructure and environment (Alcântara et al. 2023).

Since urban floods occur in a very short span of time naturally, rapid response is essential for mitigation strategies. Other traditional approaches like radars, river gauges, and weather forecasts are useful for the authorities to issue warnings. Sometimes, instant reaction is required

to save lives and infrastructure (Khan et al. 2018). The effect of urban floods can be reduced or completely avoided using the flood preventive measures, giving emergency relief and timely rescue operations (Nakhaei et al. 2023).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has been used widely in the geosciences domain now for various use cases like land use and land cover (LULC) analysis (Potlapally et al. 2019). AI technology can be helpful for the authorities in the real-time detection and understanding of urban floods (Alizadeh et al. 2022). There are few studies that have used AI for detecting real-time urban floods (Kumbam and Vejre 2024, Quang et al. 2024). Object detection is a subfield of computer vision and is used to analyse and identify the objects in an image and live stream videos (Felzenszwalb et al. 2010). You Only Look Once (YOLO) model was introduced in 2016 to detect objects in real time (Redmon et al. 2016).

This study is using YOLOv8 model to detect urban flood in both offline and real-time. We are focused on the application of the model in the UF use case and not on the development of new AI model. Authorities can take emergency operations with the help of this real-time system to save human lives and city infrastructure. It is first prototype and will be polished further and deployed upon approval from the city authorities. This paper consists of sections: Introduction, Materials and methods, Results, Discussion, Conclusion, acknowledgements, and References.

2 Materials and methods

The overall methodology of this study is shown below (Figure 1).

Figure 5. Methodology of study.

Data is fundamental to AI and to this study too. We used Roboflow platform (Roboflow 2026) to gather a dataset of 9467 images. We searched using keywords (puddle, water, flood, urban flood, water surface) and downloaded relevant datasets, contact the author for access to this specific data. We used street-level images of urban floods.

The datasets were labeled and refined using both manual and automated methods on the platform.

YOLO requires labeled images and a YAML file describing the data, so we exported the labeled data as a YAML file for model training. We divided the data into training, testing, validation sets as 70, 20, and 10 percent respectively. We used YOLOv8 model with 100 epochs, learning rate of 1e-3, batch size of 16, AdamW optimizer and augmentation set as disabled to train the model.

Model evaluation was done using precision, recall, and mean average precision metrics. A private 5G network, along with a Milesight (Milesight 2026) 5G camera of Savonia University of Applied Sciences was used to streamline real-time video to detect whether it is a flood or just a water puddle.

3 Results

Before presenting results, there is a need to explain the metrics. Table 1 explains all the metrics used briefly with respect to our use case.

Table 2 presents the results of YOLOv8 model. The model achieved 88.8% precision for the full dataset. Precision of detecting flood and water puddles from the images is 90.6% and 87.1% respectively.

Figure 2 below shows the visual results of the model with probability of flood and water puddles. Model detected the

Figure 2. Visual results of model detecting flood and water puddles.

flood and water puddles from the images and detected floods from the livestream of 5G camera at the campus. We used YouTube videos of urban floods and placed 5G camera in front of the screen and it was capturing floods in real-time.

4 Discussion

The results show that the YOLOv8 object detection model achieved strong precision and recall when distinguishing floods from normal water. This is important for flood monitoring, where quick and accurate alerts are needed to protect people and property. High recall and mean Average Precision (mAP) suggest the system is reliable for real-time detection using visual data.

The model identified floods and puddles in both static images and live video feeds. This proves that advanced computer vision can be used in urban flood management. Compared with Alizadeh et al. (2022), who used crowdsourced photos and flood gauge data, our approach with automated video feeds is more scalable and less dependent on manual data collection. Earlier work by Felzenszwalb et al. (2010) introduced cascade object detection, but YOLOv8 provides faster and real-time detection in complex city environments. Differences in results may be due to the types of datasets, sensors, and environmental conditions used. Our study used YouTube videos and live camera feeds, which offer varied scenarios and may explain differences from past work that used controlled datasets.

A major strength of this study is its use of real-time video and advanced object detection. This allows continuous monitoring with minimal human intervention. Precision, recall, and mAP give a full picture of model performance. However, there are some limitations. Training data included simulated flood scenarios from pre-captured images, which may not reflect all real-world conditions. This may make it difficult for the model to detect unusual or hard-to-see floods. Camera placement and factors like

Table 1. Explanation of evaluation metrics.

Metric	Definition
Precision (88.8%)	Percentage of detected objects that were correct. A high precision indicates fewer false positives, meaning the model does not mistakenly classify non-flood water as a flood.
Recall (75.8%)	Percentage of actual flood instances correctly detected. A lower recall suggests that some flood areas were missed, potentially due to variations in lighting, water reflections, or occlusions.
mAP@50 (83.6%)	Mean Average Precision at an IoU (Intersection over Union) threshold of 50%, which measures the overall detection accuracy. The high score indicates that the model effectively identifies flood and water objects in test images.
mAP@50-95 (55.8%)	Average precision across multiple IoU thresholds (from 50% to 95%), showing how well the model generalizes to different levels of detection strictness. The moderate score suggests room for improvement in handling more complex scenarios.

Table 2. Results of YOLO model.

Class	Images	Instances	Precision (P)	Recall (R)	mAP@50	mAP@50-95
All	1738	2018	88.8%	88.8%	83.6%	55.8%
Flood	241	297	90.6%	79.1%	84.9%	68.9%
Water	1492	1721	87.1%	72.4%	82.3%	42.6%

lighting, obstacles, and weather can also affect accuracy and introduce bias. These issues should be addressed in future studies.

High recall suggests the model can spot many types of floods. However, false positives may happen if puddles look like floods. Adding context such as rainfall, location data, or time patterns could help the model tell the difference between harmless water and dangerous flooding. The YOLOv8 architecture is good at learning spatial details, which helps it work well in busy urban scenes.

Future work should use more real-world flood footage from a range of locations to make the model stronger. Including other data types, like weather and hydrology, could improve accuracy and reduce false alarms. Testing the model under different lighting and environmental conditions will help find and fix sources of bias. Methods like transfer learning and domain adaptation may also help the model work in areas with less labelled data. In summary, combining computer vision with more data sources can lead to better and more scalable flood detection systems.

5 Conclusions

This study showed that YOLOv8 is effective for real-time flood detection. The model achieved high recall and precision for spotting floods and puddles. Using live video and advanced object detection helps monitor floods with less human effort. However, training data and camera setup can impact accuracy. Adding weather and location data could improve the results. Further testing under different conditions is needed. Future work should use diverse real flood footage to improve reliability.

In this study, we examined the role of object detection metrics in flood and water detection. Precision, recall, and mAP are key measures of model performance. Each metric supports different project requirements. For flood detection, recall and mAP@50–95 are especially important because missed floods can have serious consequences. Precision helps reduce false alarms, which is critical in areas such as security and healthcare.

Our implementation with YOLOv8 highlighted the need to distinguish between normal water accumulation and actual flooding. The model achieved high precision and recall in flood detection. However, performance can still improve in complex situations. Choosing appropriate evaluation metrics ensures that object detection models address the specific demands and challenges of each application.

Acknowledgments: This research was funded by AMBITIOUS project, Advanced CoMputing Continuum Solutions for Boosting DiGiTalIzation across European Regions from the Interregional Innovation Investments (I3) Instrument (project, number 101115116).

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